

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B036
 Date: 29 Jul 2004
 Take Off 09:52:57
 Landing: 14:57:57
 Flight Time 5h05m00

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Warm conveyor belt outflow

Operating Area: West of the Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	John Methven	Reading University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Flight Manager 2	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
8	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
9	ORAC/PAN	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
10	PERCA	Mark Jacob	Leicester University
11	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
12	WAS	Jim Hopkins	York University
13	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
14	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
15	FAGE	Cedric Floquet	Leeds University
16	Mission Scientist 2	Steve Arnold	Leeds University
17	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
18			

Track Plot:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B036
 Date: 29/07/2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093535					INU to Nav
095257		T/O	0.0 kft	269	from Horta
095500					TWC reset
095625	100401	Run 1	5.0 kft	338	
100030					PSAP flow on
100210					end J-W Cal
100401	101106	Profile 1	5.0 - 12.0 kft	289	
101003					videos recording
101114	110102	Run 2	12.0 kft	290	
101555					PSAP flow off
101743		evm1	12.0 kft	288	precipitation
102255					PSAP flow on
103000					NOxy cal complete
105635					Satcom call, CCM to DFL
105748					PSAP flow on
110036		evm2	12.0 kft	281	clear air
110110	110731	Profile 2	12.0 - 19.0 kft	280	
110120					PSAP flow off
110840	114624	Run 3	19.0 kft	203	
110919					PSAP flow on
113450					PSAP flow off
114222					PSAP flow on
114702	115018	Profile 3	19.0 - 22.0 kft	186	
115247	120339	Run 4	22.0 kft	354	
120702	121206	Run 5	22.0 kft	228	
121225	121550	Profile 4	22.0 - 25.0 kft	252	
121602	123105	Run 6	25.0 kft	253	
123112	123432	Profile 5	25.0 - 27.0 kft	268	
123755	125256	Run 7	27.0 kft	010	
123908					PSAP flow off
124210					PSAP flow on
130121	130721	Profile 6	27.0 - 22.0 kft	246	
130728	131322	Run 8	22.0 kft	246	
130831		interrupt Run	22.0 kft	246	
131047		recommence run	22.0 kft	084	
131322	133911	Profile 7	21.9 - 0.10 kft	072	1000ft/min
133055					change to 500ft/min
133912	134950	Profile 8	0.10 - 16.9 kft	086	
134150					change to 1500ft/min
134950	141536	Run 9	17.0 kft	077	
142419					PSAP flow on
141740	143913	Run 10	15.0 kft	086	
143100					PSAP flow off
143430					PSAP flow on
145757		Land	-.02 kft	269	Horta

B036 Track 29-JUL-04

39°W

37°W

35°W

33°W

31°W

29°W

27°W

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

36°N

40°N

39°N

38°N

37°N

36°N

39°W

37°W

35°W

33°W

31°W

29°W

27°W

clearance"
 location (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 at reported position
 present or last reported position (hours and minutes)
 at Level
 on assigned route or OCA entry point
 time for next position or OCA entry point
 current position
 each Number, Flight Level, or route
 information or clarifying remarks
 change in Mach Number, or route when a position report
 appropriate.
 a sequence:
 "clearance"
 location (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 each Number, or route
 information or clarifying remarks
 E:
 time for next position.
 a sequence:
 "altitude"
 location (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 of route
 time for next position (hours and minutes)
 location
 ER
 on position or time a climb to the next higher FL is
 requested for higher FLs is requested when inclusion in
 message is not appropriate.
 a sequence:
 location (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 Acceptable FLs
 time
 MESSAGE:
 or make a request in plain language that does not
 conflict with other message format. No message
 shall be inserted by the ground station.
 a sequence:
 location (additionally state frequency when using HF)
 location or request in plain language and format free.

ALTIMETER SETTING
 pressure setting for cruising flights
 in various FIRs. QNH setting on descent
 to minimum levels.

NEW YORK OCEANIC CTA/KZNY FIR
 (Unc't' below FL35)
 NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410
 SANTA MARIA OCEANIC
 CTA (A)/LIPPO FIR (G)
 (Unc't' below FL35)
 NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA RADIO

NAT A	NAT E
3016	2962
5598	0628
8906	0825
13306	11309
17946	17946

VHF
 127.90 132.07
 SELCAL
 ① 426302

① SATCOM Air-to-Ground
 COM-failure.

ORT
 N31
 W01

B036: ITOP – Warm conveyor belt outflow.

Mission Scientists: John Methven & Steve Arnold

Date: 29/07/04

Outline schedule:

06:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

08:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing

09:15 UT – Security sweep

09:30 UT – Boarding deadline

10:00 UT - Take-off

Location: West of Horta

Aim: To intercept extensive layers of polluted air west of the Azores at high altitudes (FL160-FL300), which was uplifted from the US in a warm-conveyor belt on 27/07/04. Air sampled by the DC8 on transit to the intercomparison on 28/07/04 will also be resampled.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to first available level (5000ft) for wet chemistry checks. (10)
2. T+10 Ascend to FL120 and transit to KOKER. Include at least 20 mins level in clear air for calcs. (50)
3. T+60 Exit KOKER ascending to FL190, and perform level run towards south-west until polluted feature is crossed (30).
4. T+90 Turn onto reciprocal heading and head back towards pollution maximum (15).
5. T+105 Turn to north-west and perform level run along axis of feature (20).
6. T+125 Make turn onto reciprocal heading and profile ascend to FL220 @ 500 ft/min. (10)
7. T+135 Perform level run at FL220 (15).
8. T+150 Make turn onto reciprocal heading and profile ascend to FL250 @ 500 ft/min. (10)
9. T+160 Perform level run at FL250 (15).
10. T+175 Make turn onto reciprocal heading and profile ascend to FL270 @ 500 ft/min. (5)
11. T+180 Perform level run at FL270 (15).
12. T+195 Make turn onto reciprocal heading and profile ascend to FL320 @ 500 ft/min. (10)
13. T+205 Perform level run at FL320 (15).
14. T+220 Make turn onto reciprocal heading and profile descend to 100ft @ 1000 ft/min above 5000ft and @ 500 ft/min below 5000ft. Interrupt descent at ~FL220 to allow instrument recovery.(40)
15. T+260 Make profile ascent to FL150 in direction heading towards KOKER. (20)
16. T+280 Transit back to Horta via KOKER.
17. T+340 Land.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B036	DATE: 29/07/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: West of Horta		PROJECT: ITOP – Warm conveyor belt outflow	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	- psi / - bar	- psi / - bar	- psi / - bar
POST FLIGHT	1100 psi / 75 bar	2100 psi / 135 bar	850 psi / 59 bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)
28/07/04	?	?	101..93	55.96	5704.13	-	-	-	-	-	-
18:29:22	Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.										
29/07/04	Ground	-	105.17	54.54	5736.54	-	-	-	-	-	-
08:58:51	Remarks: First cal of day.										
09:45:30	Ground	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Remarks: Power changeover forced CO to reboot but it didn't come up. Tried again manually and again it hung. Checked for a floppy still being in the drive – left by Ruth? There was so rebooted again and CO came up. Lamp off between 09:45:30 and 09:49 so there may be some loss of sensitivity of data. After lamp lit CO wasn't back to proper value until 09:50:56.										
09:51:20	Ground	-	110.28	56.26	6204.11	62.594	16	-0.11	0.37	0.27	-
	Remarks: Cal as taxiing and turning with air sample pipes closed. Continues through take off (09:52:27) and into ascent										
09:54:50	-	-	Flow Lamp: 33.98 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.98 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.17 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.33 Bar	Temp Lamp: °C	Temp Monocr: °C	Temp PMT: °C		
	Remarks:										
09:58:15	FL050	R1	104.25	56.29	5867.98	61.993	22	-0.04	0.33	0.29	-
	Remarks: Wet Chem checks run. Cal ended: 10:00:40										
10:16:15	FL120	R2	100.99	57.04	5760.25	68.185	54	-0.03	0.93	0.91	-
	Remarks: End cal: 10:18: Part of cal in precipitation. Pressure Monocr: 0.93 Pressure Cal Gas: 2.27										
11:07:30	FL190	R3									
	Remarks: CO shot up from ~70ppb to 242ppb. HORACE showed only a 110-115 ppb peak!										
11:30:00	FL190	R	98.65	56.70	5593.23	78.37	87	Cals	Cals	Cals	-
	Remarks: TECO Nox cal continued after CO finished. O3 didn't seem affected by TECO cal. End cal 11:32:25										
11:53:02	FL190	R4	99.07	56.03	5550.67	10.018	77	-0.22	0.41	0.26	-
	Remarks: Cal started 20 sec into run.										
12:16:02	FL250	R6	99.53	55.19	5492.70	105.703	72	-0.12*	0.16*	0.04*	-
			Flow Lamp: 34.01 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.84 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.15 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.19 Bar	Temp Lamp: °C	Temp Monocr: °C	Temp PMT: °C		
	Remarks: Cal started with start of run call. End cal: 12:18:33 *TECO NOx cal at same time – values from the cal										
12:55:34	FL270	R7	101.33	54.05	5477.06	110.175	85	-0.08	0.53	0.45	-
			Flow Lamp: 34.10 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.82 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.15 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.17 Bar	Temp Lamp: 49.43 °C	Temp Monocr: 23.32 °C	Temp PMT: 23.26 °C		
	Remarks: Call called for by Mission Scientist. End cal: 12:57:57										
13:07:40	FL220	R8	102.08	53.93	5505.07	102.810	76	-0.15	0.20	0.05	-
			Flow Lamp: 34.05 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.87 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.15 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.21 Bar	Temp Lamp: 49.12 °C	Temp Monocr: 23.26 °C	Temp PMT: 23.21 °C		
	Remarks: Run to let Peroxides pump catch up with pressure changes. End cal: 13:00:08										
13:50:45	FL170	R9	102.51	54.36	5572.66	75.382		Cals	Cals	Cals	-
			Flow Lamp: 34.01 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.90 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.15 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.25 Bar	Temp Lamp: 48.86 °C	Temp Monocr: 23.21 °C	Temp PMT: 23.16 °C		
	Remarks: End cal: 13:53:08										
14:18:25	FL150	R	102.00	54.42	5550.99	83.347	51	-0.05	0.14	0.10	-
			Flow Lamp: 33.96 ml/min	Pressure Monocr: 0.92 Bar	Pressure Cell: 7.15 Torr	Pressure Cal Gas: 2.26 Bar	Temp Lamp: 49.14 °C	Temp Monocr: 23.24 °C	Temp PMT: 23.21 °C		
	Remarks: End Cal: 14:20:47										
	Remarks:										
	Remarks:										
	Remarks:										
	Remarks:										

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...036.....

Date29/7/2004.....

Page1... of2

Video Tapes		GPS		INU	DRS
V8		Lat	38° 31.26 N	38° 31.26 N	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
No.		Long	28 43.00 W	28 42.98 W	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ends		Time	09 34 35	09 36 40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓ 4	✓	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
09 35 35		INU to NAV						
09 47 00		Taxi						
09 52 57		T/O from Horca						
09 55 20		TWC reset						
10 00 30		PSAP flow on						
10 02 10		end fuel end J-W cal						
10 04 01		end run 1, start PI ↑ 1000 ft/min						
10 10 03		Videos recording						
10 15 55		PSAP flow off						
10 19 27		PSAP flow on						
10 22 55		PSAP flow off						
10 30 00		NOxy cal complete						
10 56 35		SATCOM-H call, COM → DR						
10 57 48		PSAP flow on						
11 01 20		PSAP flow off						
11 09 19		PSAP flow on						
11 34 50		PSAP flow off					*	
11 42 22		PSAP flow ON						
12 16 02	FM	PC crash						
12 39 08		PSAP flow off						into icing cloud
13 42 10		PSAP flow on						
13 13 22		Start of profile 7						
13 30 35		change to 580 ft/min						
13 38 00		All cameras We logged on descent						
13 41 50		climb at 1500 ft/min						
13 49 50		Run 9 started at end of profile						

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B036 29/7/2004

Instruments

No ADIR data.

Flt Manager's display set on wrong mode on turn on - unable to support graphics resolution of PC. Reset monitor by putting the power connection out / putting in again.

Aircraft